

Selfie and Marketing of Domestic Tourism

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ABSTRACT

Selfie is a trending technology around the world. Various studies have documented on selfie but few related to marketing of domestic tourism. The aim of this paper was to examine selfie and marketing of domestic tourism with the specific objective of establishing the relationship between selfie usage and promotion of domestic tourism. Theoretical framework approach is guided by diffusion theory. The study area is Dar es Salaam, Tanzania. Snowballing sampling technique was used and survey semi-structured questionnaires were sent to a sample size of 60. The collected quantitative data was subjected to descriptive statistics, Chi-square test and ANOVA. Among the ANOVA findings in the relationship between selfie usage and promotion of domestic tourism revealed that there is a statistically significant relationship between using selfie to learning about tourist attractions visited and marketing activities uses effective means of promotion and advertising for domestic tourism ($p = 0.032$). The study contributes knowledge about selfie and marketing of domestic tourism in the context of Tanzania.

Keyword: *selfie, marketing, domestic tourism, Tanzania*

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Selfie as a personal media is considered to be popular (Cruz & Thornham, 2015). Advances in technology and continuous changes within the society particularly the knowledge society has created the need for information sharing. Various articles have researched issues in relation to selfie (Edmondson, 2014; Cruz & Thornham, 2015; Paris & Pietschnig, 2015; Senft & Baym, 2015; Loveless *et al.*, 2016; Elmahdy, Haukeland & Fredman, 2017; Hockert, Luthje & Ilola, 2017; Kadir & Zulfakho, 2017). The study by Edmondson (2014) examined practices of personal archive, self fashion and gender in contemporary photo album. Other scholars such as Elmahdy *et al.* (2017)

were investigating tourism megatrends and mentioned that one of the megatrends in tourism is social media where people share information while Pearce and Moscardo (2015) studied social representations of tourist selfies by examining photo taking and photo sharing behaviour on social media.

Although selfie is a phenomenon under study by various scholars, there is still limited research on selfie and marketing of domestic tourism. Previous research highly focused on selfies in terms of trends, behaviour and its impact on some tourist destinations. Tanzania like other countries face challenges in promoting attractions and this is a problem which has been mentioned by previous and current scholars (Mariki *et al.*, 2011; Macha, 2016). In addition, promotion challenges exist particularly in engaging new trends such as selfie in marketing of domestic tourism. Therefore, in adding knowledge to the phenomenon of selfie as a technology for the knowledge society in relation to domestic tourism, this study examines selfie and marketing of domestic tourism. The specific objective of this study is to establish the relationship between selfie usage and promotion of domestic tourism.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Concepts Definition

Selfie is generally defined as a photograph that one has taken of oneself or self-portrait photography taken using a digital camera or phone camera held in the hand or supported by a selfie stick (Merriam-Webster, 2014; Kwon & Kwon, 2015; Pearce & Moscardo, 2017; Safna, 2017). These selfies are then shared with social media platforms like Facebook or Twitter (Safna, 2017). The popularity of selfies taken during travels has prompted hotels to offer guests with selfie sticks (Paris & Pietschnig, 2015). Selfies are also considered as a new form of digital tourist photography (Larsen, 2008). For marketers, selfies indicate that individuals are young, fun and connected (Senft & Baym, 2015). For purposes of this study, selfie is a photograph taken of oneself in tourist attractions using a digital camera or phone camera.

2.2 Marketing of Domestic Tourism

Marketing involves 7Ps and according to Al-Debi (2014), the 7Ps are product, price, place, promotion, people, physical evidence and process. In marketing of domestic tourism for the knowledge society, this study is interested in the 4th Marketing mix called promotion. Tanzania faces a number of promotion challenges for domestic tourism including inadequate use of media, high transport costs, travel culture and tourism awareness (Anderson, 2010; Lwoga, 2011; Mariki *et al.*, 2011; Macha, 2016). Recent studies indicate that marketing engages promotion of domestic tourism whereby television is also widely used in Tanzania for TV programs showing national parks (Mkwizu, 2016; Mkwizu, 2017a, 2017b; Mkwizu, Matama & Atuzarirwe, 2017; Mkwizu, 2018). This paper focuses on marketing of domestic tourism in the context of Tanzania. For this study, marketing of domestic tourism refers to the promotion of travel within Tanzania by residents visiting tourist attractions through information sharing such as social media.

2.3 Theoretical Literature Review

The Diffusion theory is a theory which was initially developed by Ryan and Gross in 1943 (Surry, 1997). Diffusion theory assumes the existence on the spread of ideas and actions within social systems in relation to innovations (Rogers, 1995; Surry, 1997; Green, Ottoson, Garcia, Hiatt & Roditis, 2014). Furthermore, Green *et al.* (2014) indicated that the occurrence of diffusion of ideas or rather innovation is characterized by repetition, opposition and adaption. Selfie as a technological phenomenon is considered to be popular and has spread among users particularly the youth. From previous studies such as Paris and Pietschnig (2015), Kadir and Zulfakho (2017), and Safna (2017), it can be concluded that selfies as a technological innovation has undergone stages of repetition, opposition in the sense that the impact of selfies is both negative and positive and thus individuals will adapt the selfie innovation depending on various situations or personality traits.

Over the years the Diffusion Theory has developed from the assumption of the spread of ideas and actions to its association with innovation. Other scholars have used the Diffusion Theory to study aspects in tourism. For instance, Anderson (2010) used the Diffusion Theory to explain investment in tourism development. While other studies used Diffusion Theory on investment issues related to tourism, this study adopts the Diffusion Theory to guide the analysis of selfie usage in relation to marketing of domestic tourism. Selfie as a trendy technology is spreading in various parts of the world including Tanzania. This study hypothesizes that there is a statistically significant relationship between selfie usage and promotion of domestic tourism.

2.4 Empirical Literature Review

Selfie as a technology has been made popular through social media platforms like Wechat and Facebook (Kadir & Zufakho, 2017). Individuals searching for information on places to go also use social media platforms where there is access to selfies taken in various destinations. Selfies taken by individuals during their travels allow others to experience new and unknown destinations (Elmahdy *et al.*, 2017). The study by Elmahdy *et al.* (2017) was conducted in Norway using a Delphi methodology approach and found that one of the megatrends in tourism particularly for nature based tourism is technological trends in terms of ICT which includes the use of social media platforms for information dissemination.

On the other hand, a study by Safna (2017) researched in Sri Lanka explored impacts of selfies on youth and using a descriptive methodological approach found that there were negative impacts of selfies on the youth which include skin damage, loss of confidence and self esteem. Whereas other studies on selfies concentrate on trends and impact, the research by Paris and Pietschnig (2015) was interested on personality traits of travel selfies. Paris and Pietschnig (2015) conducted a study in the United Arab Emirates and findings using multiple regression analysis revealed that agreeable individuals showed more positive attitudes towards taking selfies when travelling. Although the study by Paris and Pietschnig (2015) was on travel selfies related to tourism, there is still limited literature on selfies as a phenomenon in the perspective of marketing domestic tourism.

In Africa, Stone and Nyaupane (2017) indicated that there is limited research on domestic tourism in Botswana and Africa in general. Other studies (Mkwizu & Matama, 2017; Singa'mbi & Lwoga, 2017; Mbilinyi, 2017) have contributed literature on various issues on domestic tourism such as millennials, heritage and culinary but these are still very few studies according to Stone and Nyaupane (2017). There is also the persistent problem particularly in marketing domestic tourism where promotion efforts need to be increased so as to boost domestic tourism. A number of scholars in Africa have highlighted on insufficient promotion of domestic tourism (Macha, 2016, Stone & Nyaupane, 2017). A recent study by Mkwizu (2017a) indicated that domestic tourists contribute 40.5% of total visitors to national parks in Tanzania. However, there is limited literature from previous studies on selfies in relation to tourism, and there is even less research in the context of Tanzania. Therefore, in filling the knowledge gap, this study examines selfie and marketing of domestic tourism.

2.5 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for this study is guided by diffusion theory and empirical literature review. The independent variable is selfie and the dependent variable is marketing of domestic tourism. The hypothesis H_1 states that there is a statistically significant relationship between selfie usage and promotion of domestic tourism.

3.0 DATA & METHODOLOGY

This study used quantitative research approach to facilitate the testing of hypothesis H_1 which states that there is a statistically significant relationship between selfie usage and promotion of domestic tourism. Area of study is Dar es Salaam in Tanzania at The Open University of Tanzania. Unit of

analysis is university graduates who are selfie users for domestic tourism purposes. Survey semi structured questionnaires were sent out to a sample size of 60 respondents by email using snowballing sampling since the number of selfie users is not known. The measurement for the variables of selfie usage were adopted and customized from Pearse and Moscardo (2015), and Kwon and Kwon (2015). Selfies usage was measured using eleven statements.

The eleven statements for selfie usage are; use selfie to seek a particular photographic image of tourist attractions (SU1); use selfie as a motivation to connect the tourist attractions I have visited (SU2); use selfie to learn about tourist attractions I have visited (SU3); use selfie to build self awareness of tourist attractions I have visited (SU4); use selfie to share photographic images of tourist attractions with family and friends (SU5); use selfie as a motivation to connect with friends and families on the tourist attractions (SU6); use selfie to take photographs alone in the visited tourist attractions (SU7); take selfies as a group in the visited tourist attractions (SU8); use selfie to share with friends & family on tourist attractions I have visited (SU9); use selfie to share my photographs on social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp and Twitter on tourist attractions I have visited (SU10); and visited tourist attractions and taken selfies (SU11).

The measurement for marketing of domestic tourism using promotion were adopted and customized from Al-Debi (2014), and Singh and Bhowal (2011). Promotion was measured using six statements coded as P1, P2, P3, P4, P5 and P6: uses of effective means of promotion and advertising (P1); focuses on personal selling as an effective means of promotion (P2); there is adequate allocation of budget for promotional activities (P3); rich information and data about domestic tourism from the internet (P4); experiences from others that they enjoy sharing information on domestic tourism (P5); and promotion prices from tourism authorities or entities in tourist attractions that I visit (P6). The scale of measurement used for the statements are five-Point Likert scale of strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5).

Validity and reliability was done using a pilot study and Cronbach's alpha. The Cronbach's alpha for selfie usage (0.869), and marketing for domestic tourism (0.804). Field (2014) mentioned that for reliability, the Cronbach's alpha value of 0.70 and above is acceptable. In order to describe the sample characteristics and test the hypothesized relationships of this paper, the returned 35 questionnaires were subjected to quantitative analysis using descriptive statistics, Chi-Square test and ANOVA supported by SPSS Version 20. Due to the small sample size of this study, ANOVA as a non- parametric was used for analysis of the collected data. Fagerland (2012) and Nahm (2016) mentioned that non parametric tests are useful for small sample size.

4.0 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The characteristics of the respondents are shown in Table 1. The findings show that a majority of the respondents are aged between 26 to 35 years (51.4%), male (60%), earn a monthly income above TZS 300,000 (97.1%), are university graduates (100%), and take selfies using a smart phone (82.9%). This suggests that respondents are young male adults with monthly income above TZS 300,000 and are university graduates who take selfies using smart phones.

Table 1. Characteristics of Respondents

Variable	Frequencies (n)	Percentage (%)	
Age :	26-35	18	51.4
	36-45	13	37.1
	46-55	4	11.4
Gender:	Male	21	60
	Female	14	40
Income per month: Tanzania Shillings (TZS)	< 300,000 TZS	1	2.9
	>300,000 TZS	34	97.1

Highest Education: University	35	100
Selfie taken by: Smart Phone	29	82.9
Digital Camera	3	8.6
iPad	1	2.9
Tablet	1	2.9
Others	1	2.9

Source: Field data (2018)

The findings of Chi-square test in Table 2 show that there is a statistically significant relationship between selfie usage and promotion of domestic tourism which is explained by (i) (SU3) using selfies to learn about tourist attractions that respondents visited and (P5) hear experiences from others that they enjoy sharing information about domestic tourism ($p = 0.007$), (ii) (SU4) using selfies to build self awareness of tourist attractions that respondents visited and (P5) hear experiences from others that they enjoy sharing information about domestic tourism ($p = 0.054$), (iii) (SU5) using selfies to share photographic images with family and friends and (P5) hear experiences from others that they enjoy sharing information about domestic tourism ($p = 0.040$), (iv) (SU7) using selfies to take photographs alone in the visited tourist attractions and (P1) marketing activities uses effective means of promotion and advertising for domestic tourism ($p = 0.012$).

Furthermore, the findings in Table 2 show that there is a statistically significant relationship between selfie usage and promotion of domestic tourism which can be explained by v) (SU7) using selfies to take photographs alone in the visited tourist attractions and (P5) hear experiences from others that they enjoy sharing information about domestic tourism ($p = 0.032$), vi) (SU8) using selfies as a group in the visited tourist attractions and (P5) hear experiences from others that they enjoy sharing information about domestic tourism ($p = 0.000$), vii) (SU9) using selfies to share with friends and family on tourist attractions visited and (P1) feel that marketing activities by tourism authorities and agents focuses on personal selling as effective means of promoting domestic tourism ($p = 0.032$).

Findings of Table 2 also revealed that there is a statistically significant relationship between selfie usage and promotion of domestic tourism through, (viii) (SU9) using selfies to share with friends and family on tourist attractions visited and (P5) hear experiences from others that they enjoy sharing information about domestic tourism ($p = 0.002$), xi) (SU11) have visited tourist attractions and taken selfies and (P1) marketing activities uses effective means of promotion and advertising for domestic tourism ($p = 0.046$), and x) (SU11) have visited tourist attractions and taken selfies and (P5) hear experiences from others that they enjoy sharing information about domestic tourism ($p = 0.025$). All the remaining statements were not statistically significant.

Table 2. Chi-square test selfie usage and promotion of domestic tourism

	Value	Asymp.Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square for (SU3 and P5)	32.980 ^a	0.007
Pearson Chi-square for (SU4 and P5)	25.991 ^a	0.054
Pearson Chi-square for (SU5 and P5)	27.114 ^a	0.040
Pearson Chi-square for (SU7 and P1)	31.364 ^a	0.012
Pearson Chi-square for (SU7 and P5)	27.919 ^a	0.032
Pearson Chi-square for (SU8 and P5)	54.088 ^a	0.000
Pearson Chi-square for (SU9 and P1)	27.996 ^a	0.032
Pearson Chi-square for (SU9 and P5)	37.542 ^a	0.002
Pearson Chi-square for (SU11 and P1)	26.572 ^a	0.046
Pearson Chi-square for (SU11 and P5)	28.892 ^a	0.025

Source: Field data (2018)

ANOVA findings in Appendix I shows that (i) there is a statistically significant relationship between *using selfie to learn about tourist attractions I have visited and marketing activities uses effective means of promotion and advertising for domestic tourism* ($p = 0.032$), and (ii) there is a statistically significant relationship between *using selfie to learn about tourist attractions I have visited and feel that marketing activities by tourism authorities and agents focuses on personal selling as an effective means of promoting domestic tourism* ($p = 0.024$). The rest of the relationships were insignificant. The ANOVA findings in Appendix II shows that there is a statistically significant relationship between using selfie as a motivation to connect with friends and families on the tourist attractions I have visited and hearing experiences from others that they enjoy sharing information about domestic tourism ($p = 0.048$). The rest are not statistically significant.

ANOVA findings in Appendix III shows that there is a statistically significant relationship between taking selfies as a group in the visited tourist attractions and hearing experiences from others that they enjoy sharing information about domestic tourism ($p = 0.002$). The rest are not statistically significant. ANOVA findings in Appendix IV shows that (i) there is a statistically significant relationship between *using selfies to share with friends and family on tourist attractions I have visited and I feel that marketing activities by tourism authorities and agents focuses on personal selling as effective means of promoting domestic tourism* ($p = 0.008$), and (ii) there is a statistically significant relationship between *using selfies to share with friends and family on tourist attractions I have visited and hearing experiences from others that they enjoy sharing information about domestic tourism* ($p = 0.024$). The rest of the relationships are not statistically significant.

The characteristics results of this study differs from the study by Safna (2017) suggesting that there are no negative impacts in selfies and this is because the young male adults in this current study use selfies widely with their smart phones and further results by Chi-square test and ANOVA indicate that there is a statistically significant relationship between selfie usage and promotion of domestic tourism. The results of this study further support the diffusion theory and that selfie as innovation is spread amongst university graduates and widely used for tourism purposes.

5.0 CONCLUSION

This main objective of this paper was to examine selfie and marketing of domestic tourism. This study specifically establishes the relationship between selfie usage and promotion of domestic tourism. Results indicated that there is a statistically significant relationship between selfie usage and promotion of domestic tourism which is explained by a) using selfie to learn about tourist attractions visited and marketing activities uses effective means of promotion and advertising for domestic tourism, b) using selfie to learn about tourist attractions visited and feel that marketing activities by tourism authorities and agents focuses on personal selling as effective means of promoting domestic tourism, c) using selfie as a motivation to connect with friends and families on the tourist attractions visited and hear experiences from others that they enjoy sharing information about domestic tourism, d) taking selfies as a group in the visited tourist attractions and hear experiences from others that they enjoy sharing information about domestic tourism, and e) using selfie to share with friends and family on tourist attractions visited and feel that marketing activities by tourism authorities and agents focuses on personal selling as an effective means of promoting domestic tourism.

The implications of the study outcome is for the tourism sector to encourage selfies in tourist attractions that are visited by tourists such as university graduates due to the statistically significant results between selfie usage and promotion of domestic tourism. Theoretically, the study results of statistically significant relationship support the diffusion theory in that selfie as an innovation is widely used amongst university graduates through the use of smart phones or other gadgets like tablets and iPad serve as information source to share photos and tourists attractions with friends and family within the society, and thus help in creating tourism information for the

knowledge society. Future researchers can examine similar relationships amongst international tourists visiting tourist attractions in order to enrich the understanding of the selfie phenomenon.

REFERENCES

- Al-Debi, H.A. (2013). "The impact of services marketing mix 7P's in competitive advantage to five Stars Hotel-Case study Amman, Jordan." *International Academic Conference* 39-48.
- Anderson, W. (2010). "Marketing of Domestic Tourism in Tanzania". Dar es Salaam University Press. ISBN 978-9976-60-454-8.
- Cruz, E.G., & Thornham, H. (2015). "Selfies beyond self-representation: the theoretical frictions of practice." *Journal of Aesthetics & Culture* 7: 1-10.
- Edmondson, C.M.S. (2014). "A rebirth of exteriority: The socio-visual circulation of self in the 19th Century and Today. 1-136. Retrieved from http://comm.stanford.edu/mm/2013/01/Chloe-Edmondson_MA-Thesis.pdf
- Elmady, Y.M., Haukelnad, J.V., & Fredman, P. (2017). "Tourism megatrends, a literature review focused on nature-based tourism." 3-74.
<http://www.umb.no/statisk/ina/publikasjoner/fagrappport/if42.pdf>
- Fragerland, M. W. (2012). "t-test, non-parametric tests, and large studies- a paradox of statistical practice?" *BMC Medical Research Methodology* 12: 78. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2288-12-78>
- Field, A. (2014). "Discovering statistics using IBM SPSS statistics 4th ed. Los Angeles, London, ISBN 978-4462-4917-8.
- Green, L., Ottoson, M.J., Garcia, C., Hiatt, A.R., & Roditis, L.M. (2014). "Diffusion Theory and knowledge dissemination, utilization and integration." *Frontiers in Public Health Services & Systems Research* 3(1): 1-9.
<http://uknowledge.uky.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1091&context=frontiersinphssr>
- Hockert, E., Luthje, M., & Ilola, H. (2017). "Gaze and faces in tourist photography." *Critical Tourism Studies Proceedings* 2017(1): 1.
- Kadir, S.A., & Zulfakho, N.Z. (2017). "The impact of selfie for students satisfaction: A proposed framework." *Research Hub* 3(11): 2180-0065.
- Kwon, Y.J., & Kwon, K.N. (2015). "Consuming the objectified self: The quest for authentic self." *Asian Social Science* 11(2): 301-312.
- Larsen, J. (2008). "Practices and flows of digital photography: An ethnographic framework." *Mobilities* 3(1): 141-160.
- Loveness, D.J., Beverly, C.L., Bodle, A., Dredger, K.S., Foucar-Szocki, D., Harris, T., Kang, S.L., Thall, J.B., & Wishon, P. (2016). "The vulnerability of teaching and learning selfie society. 1-25. <https://www.sensepublishers.com/media/2977-the-vulnerability-of-teaching-and-learning-in-a-selfie-society.pdf>
- Lwoga, N.B. (2011). "Tourism: Meaning, Practices and History". Dar es Salaam: Dar es Salaam University Press. ISBN 978-9976-60-539-9
- Macha, L.J. (2016). "Factors influencing participation in domestic tourism as competitive advantage for organizations within as a tourist destination." In; Proceedings of the International Conference on Tourism and Hospitality Innovations in Developing Countries Dar es Salaam, Tanzania. 189-205.
- Mariki, S.B., Hassan, S.N., Maganga, S.L.S., Modest, R.B., & Salehe, F.S. (2011). "Wildlife-Based Domestic Tourism in Tanzania: Experiences from the Northern Tourist Circuit." 62-73.
<http://www.ajol.info/index.php/ejesm/article/view/73349/62278>
- Merriam-Webster. (2014). "Selfie". <http://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/selfie>
- Mkwizu, K.H. (2016). "Intra-Destination Television Advertising on Domestic Tourism in Tanzania." *International Journal of Business & Management* 4(7): 424-430.

- Mkwizu, K.H. (2017a). "Influence of Media and Income on Domestic Tourists visiting Udzungwa National Park, Tanzania." In; Proceedings of the 10th ATLAS Africa Conference. Eldoret, Kenya. 60. Retrieved from <http://www.atlas-euro.org/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=B43I-BWOAdc%3d&tabid=261&language=en-US>
- Mkwizu, K.H. (2017b). "Promotion of National Parks for Domestic Tourism in Tanzania." *International Journal of Business and Management* 5(7): 146-150.
- Mkwizu, K.H. (2018). "Media and Sources of Market for Domestic Tourism in Tanzania: A study of Kitulo National Park in Tanzania." *International Journal of Innovative Research and Development* 7(2): 107-112.
- Mkwizu, K.H., & Matama, R. (2017). "Millennials Age Group and Income Levels among Domestic Tourists in Tanzania". *International Journal of Research and Methodology in Social Sciences* 3(4): 48-54
- Mkwizu, K.H., Matama, R., & Atuzarirwe, C. (2017). "Media and Education: Domestic Tourists' Perspective." In; Proceedings of the 14th Annual World Congress of Academy for Global Business Advancement. Eldoret, Kenya. 172. http://agba.us/pdf/2017_agba_book_abstracts.pdf
- Mbilinyi, D.B. (2017). "Investigating of tourists' total dining experiences in Tanzania." In; Proceedings of the 10th ATLAS Africa Conference. Eldoret, Kenya. 57. Retrieved from <http://www.atlas-euro.org/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=B43I-BWOAdc%3d&tabid=261&language=en-US>
- Nahm, F.S. (2016). "Nonparametric statistical tests for the continuous data: the basic concept and the practical use." *Korean Journal of Anesthesiology* 69(1): 8-14.
- Paris, C.M., & Pietschnig, J. (2015). "But first, let me take a selfie: Personality traits as predictors of travel selfie taking and sharing behaviors." *Tourism Travel and Research Association: Advancing Tourism Research Globally* 1-7. Retrieved from <http://scholarworks.umass.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1138&context=ttra>
- Pearce, J., & Moscardo, G. (2015). "Social representations of tourist selfies: New challenges for sustainable tourism." *BEST EN Think Tank XV. The Environment – People Nexus in Sustainable Tourism: Finding the Balance* 59-73.
- Rogers, E. (1995). "Diffusion of Innovations."
<http://web.stanford.edu/class/symsys205/Diffusion%20of%20Innovations.htm>
- Safna, H.M.F. (2017). "Negative Impact of Selfies on Youth." *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology Research* 5(3): 68-73.
- Senft, T., & Baym, N.K. (2015). "What does the selfie say? Investigating a global phenomenon." *International Journal of Communication* 9, 1588-1606.
- Singh, R., & Bhowal, A. (2011). "Development of marketing-driven measure of risk perception." *Journal of Risk Finance* 12(2): 140-152.
- Singa'mbi, E., & Lwoga, N.B. (2017). Heritage attachment and domestic tourists decision to visit Bagamoyo historic town. In; Proceedings of the 10th ATLAS Africa Conference. Eldoret, Kenya. 88. Retrieved from <http://www.atlas-euro.org/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=B43I-BWOAdc%3d&tabid=261&language=en-US>
- Stone, L., & Nyaupane, G. (2017). "The Tourist gaze: Local versus international tourists." In; Proceedings of the 10th ATLAS Africa Conference. Eldoret, Kenya. 90. Retrieved from <http://www.atlas-euro.org/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=B43I-BWOAdc%3d&tabid=261&language=en-US>
- Surry, W.D. (1997). "Diffusion Theory and Instructional Technology." In; Proceedings of the Annual Conference of the Association for Educational Communication and Technology (AECT). 12-15 February 1997, Albuquerque, New Mexico. Retrieved from <http://www2.gsu.edu/~wwwitr/docs/diffusion/>

APPENDIX

Appendix 1. ANOVA results for Selfie Usage and Promotion of Domestic Tourism

		Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Marketing activities uses effective means of promotion and advertising for domestic tourism.	Between Groups	13.043	3.261	3.047	0.032
	Within Groups	32.100	1.070		
	Total	45.143			
I feel that marketing activities by tourism authorities and agents focuses on personal selling as an effective means of promoting domestic tourism.	Between Groups	10.936	2.734	3.287	0.024
	Within Groups	24.950	0.832		
	Total	35.886			
I feel there is adequate allocation of budget for promotional activities for domestic tourism.	Between Groups	3.134	0.783	0.513	0.727
	Within Groups	45.838	1.528		
	Total	48.971			
I feel there is rich information and data about domestic tourism from the internet.	Between Groups	8.534	2.133	1.176	0.341
	Within Groups	54.438	1.815		
	Total	62.971			
I get to hear experiences from others that they enjoy sharing information about domestic tourism.	Between Groups	3.750	0.937	0.767	0.555
	Within Groups	36.650	1.222		
	Total	40.400			
I get promotion prices from tourism authorities or entities in tourist attractions that I visit.	Between Groups	8.962	2.241	0.901	0.476
	Within Groups	74.638	2.488		
	Total	83.600			

Source: Field data (2018)

Appendix 2. ANOVA results for Selfie Usage and Promotion of Domestic Tourism

		Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Marketing activities uses effective means of promotion and advertising for domestic tourism.	Between Groups	3.173	0.793	0.567	0.688
	Within Groups	41.970	1.399		
	Total	45.143			
I feel that marketing activities by tourism authorities and agents focuses on personal selling as an effective means of promoting domestic tourism.	Between Groups	7.921	1.980	2.124	0.102
	Within Groups	27.965	0.932		
	Total	35.886			
I feel there is adequate allocation of budget for promotional activities for domestic tourism.	Between Groups	1.007	0.252	0.157	0.958
	Within Groups	47.965	1.599		
	Total	48.971			
I feel there is rich information and data about domestic tourism from the internet.	Between Groups	6.037	1.509	0.795	0.538
	Within Groups	56.934	1.898		
	Total	62.971			
I get to hear experiences	Between Groups	10.764	2.691	2.724	0.048

from others that they enjoy sharing information about domestic tourism.	Within Groups	29.636	0.988	1.121	0.365
	Total	40.400			
	Between Groups	10.873	2.718		
I get promotion prices from tourism authorities or entities in tourist attractions that I visit.	Within Groups	72.727	2.424		
	Total	83.600			

Source: Field data (2018)

Appendix 3. ANOVA results for Selfie Usage and Promotion of Domestic Tourism

		Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Marketing activities uses effective means of promotion and advertising for domestic tourism.	Between Groups	9.012	2.253	1.871	0.142
	Within Groups	36.131	1.204		
	Total	45.143			
I feel that marketing activities by tourism authorities and agents focuses on personal selling as an effective means of promoting domestic tourism.	Between Groups	4.937	1.234	1.196	0.333
	Within Groups	30.948	1.032		
	Total	35.886			
I feel there is adequate allocation of budget for promotional activities for domestic tourism.	Between Groups	7.344	1.836	1.323	0.284
	Within Groups	41.627	1.388		
	Total	48.971			
I feel there is rich information and data about domestic tourism from the internet.	Between Groups	6.796	1.699	0.907	0.472
	Within Groups	56.176	1.873		
	Total	62.971			
I get to hear experiences from others that they enjoy sharing information about domestic tourism.	Between Groups	17.096	4.274	5.502	0.002
	Within Groups	23.304	0.777		
	Total	40.400			
I get promotion prices from tourism authorities or entities in tourist attractions that I visit.	Between Groups	8.902	2.226	0.894	0.480
	Within Groups	74.698	2.490		
	Total	83.600			

Source: Field data (2018)

Appendix 4. ANOVA results for Selfie Usage and Promotion of Domestic Tourism

		Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Marketing activities uses effective means of promotion and advertising for domestic tourism.	Between Groups	5.890	1.473	1.125	0.363
	Within Groups	39.253	1.308		
	Total	45.143			
I feel that marketing activities by tourism authorities and agents focuses on personal selling as an effective means of promoting domestic tourism.	Between Groups	13.005	3.251	4.263	0.008
	Within Groups	22.881	0.763		
	Total	35.886			

I feel there is adequate allocation of budget for promotional activities for domestic tourism.	Between Groups	4.180	1.045	0.700	0.598
	Within Groups	44.791	1.493		
	Total	48.971			
I feel there is rich information and data about domestic tourism from the internet.	Between Groups	3.995	0.999	0.508	0.730
	Within Groups	58.977	1.966		
	Total	62.971			
I get to hear experiences from others that they enjoy sharing information about domestic tourism.	Between Groups	12.274	3.069	3.273	0.024
	Within Groups	28.126	0.938		
	Total	40.400			
I get promotion prices from tourism authorities or entities in tourist attractions that I visit.	Between Groups	6.094	1.523	0.590	0.673
	Within Groups	77.506	2.584		
	Total	83.600			

Source: Field data (2018)